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D5.1 Project's branding: logo, aesthetics, website, and social media presence

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5.	Partner	Austrian Institute of Technology, GmbH	AIT	Austria
6.	Partner	Aarhus University	AU	Denmark
7.	Partner	National Technical University of Athens	NTUA	Greece
8.	Partner	European Association of Research Managers & Administrators	EARMA	European network
9.	Partner	European Citizen Science Association	ECSA	European network
10.	Partner	Korean University	KU	Korea
11.	Partner	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona	UAB	Spain
12.	Partner	University of Cape Town	UCT	South Africa
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List of abbreviations

DEC	Dissemination, exploitation, and communication
R&I	Research & innovation
SEO	Search engine optimisation
WP	Work package

Executive summary

RE4GREEN is dedicated to advancing the Green Transition by developing a comprehensive ethics and integrity framework for research and innovation (R&I) that integrates environmental ethics reflections into research ethics. To achieve this goal, RE4GREEN will collaborate with a multidisciplinary group of stakeholders, including representatives from academia, civil society, policy, and industry. Ensuring a strong and inclusive brand identity is crucial for engaging these diverse audiences and promoting wide uptake of the project findings.

This report outlines the project's visual identity and applications thereof, encompassing its logo, colour palette, and typography across its social media platforms, website, and templates. It also details how these elements align with and support RE4GREEN's core objective.

Introduction

RE4GREEN project summary

Environmental and climate-related challenges are global and reach all sectors of society. However, research and innovation (R&I) activities that address these challenges may carry substantial unintended implications. RE4GREEN aims to contribute to a European Research Area ethics and integrity framework for R&I activities designed to reduce the risk from such implications and to support the transition to a sustainable economy and society as envisioned by the European Green Deal. RE4GREEN will reflect diverse stakeholder views and relate them to cross-cutting environmental and climate-related ethics issues by applying a bottom-up social lab methodology. RE4GREEN's framework will consist of operational research ethics and integrity guidelines, recommendations, and training materials for researchers, ethics and integrity experts and advisors, and ethics reviewers to ensure R&I activities support the Green Transition.

RE4GREEN seeks to bring together a diverse and multidisciplinary group of researchers, members of ethics committees and integrity bodies, civil society organisations, policymakers, and industry representatives to shape a holistic ethics and integrity framework for R&I that supports the Green Transition. **Given the ambitious nature of this core objective, the RE4GREEN project requires a unique, bold, and consistent visual identity.**

The project's dissemination, exploitation, and communication (DEC) work package, WP5, led by NTUA, will enhance the visibility of RE4GREEN's progress and outputs throughout the project's duration. In this capacity, WP5 will act as a bridge between RE4GREEN and relevant stakeholders to boost the uptake of project results. Given the cardinal role of dissemination and communication in raising project awareness, DEC activities must be supported by powerful branding.

This report introduces the branding strategy for RE4GREEN, presenting its visual identity within the project's social media channels, website, and templates.

Branding

Logo

The RE4GREEN logo, shown in Figure 1, serves as the primary visual identifier for the project. It acts as the cornerstone of all dissemination and communication efforts, representing the project's identity and ensuring recognisability across various platforms.

Figure 1: The RE4GREEN logo on a light background; the globe-shaped icon transitioning from a darker colour to a greener shade.

The graphic element of the logo features a globe-shaped and plant leaf shaped illustration, symbolising sustainability. Inspired by the shape of the Earth, it reflects the need for an environmental transition from a darker, greyer state to a greener one. This imagery represents the shift from the current climate and environmental crisis towards a sustainable, greener economy and society. Variations of the project's logo are depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Variations of the RE4GREEN logo.

Colour palette and Texture

The colour palette of RE4GREEN is presented in Figure 3. The varying sizes of the colour areas reflect, in a semi-quantitative way, the prominence each colour should have across RE4GREEN's dissemination and communication channels. This colour palette has been chosen to reflect the associations that the WP5 leaders along with the coordination team have chosen for the branding, namely "sustainability, minimalism, Green Transition, society" (Figure 4). This mood fosters an environment closely linked to sustainability applications. The colour palette represents a visual leitmotif that creates a sense of unity throughout the dissemination and communication channels of RE4GREEN.

The texture effect, depicted in Figure 5, is applied widely in RE4GREEN branding and adds to the recognisability of the project materials. Many aspects of the RE4GREEN branding can be combined with the texture effect according to the preferences of the consortium (see Figure 6).

Figure 3: The colour palette of RE4GREEN.

Figure 4: The mood board of RE4GREEN.

Figure 5: The RE4GREEN texture effect.

Figure 6: Uses of the RE4GREEN texture effect.

Typography

A successful selection and use of typography boosts brand personality and ensures clarity and harmony across RE4GREEN DEC activities. Figure 6 depicts the typographic elements to be applied in all dissemination and communication activities of the project.

Aa

Montserrat Alternates

**ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
123457890**

Montserrat Alternates Extra Bold

Aa

Urbanist

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
123457890

Urbanist Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
123457890

Urbanist Regular Italic

**ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
123457890**

Urbanist Extra Bold

**ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
123457890**

Urbanist Extra Bold Italic

Figure 6: The primary (upper) and secondary (lower) typography of RE4GREEN.

Application of RE4GREEN branding

This section describes the application of the RE4GREEN branding across the main dissemination and communication channels of the project, including its social media platforms, website, and PowerPoint and deliverable templates.

Website

The RE4GREEN website can be found under the domain name re4green.eu. It provides concise, high-level project information; acts as the focal point of the project's online dissemination channels, i.e., X and LinkedIn; and links viewers to relevant networks and platforms.

The website was designed during the first three months of the project, in collaboration with the management and coordination team at UBO, and was launched in May 2024.

The website

- Is responsive, meaning that it adapts to different devices without affecting the website's format.
- Is accessible, being built in accordance, where possible, with the [web content accessibility guidelines](#).
- Includes search engine optimisation (SEO) best practices, with its content and code structured for optimal search engine understanding.

Websites that are responsive, accessible, and include SEO best practices rank higher in Google search results. One can measure these factors using tools like [PageSpeed Insights](#).

Below, we present a series of screen captures from the mock-ups of the project's website. As the project matures, its progress and results will be featured in dedicated sections. As a result, the website will undergo frequent updates. The RE4GREEN website will be hosted on NTUA's server until three years after the end of the project, as specified in the Grant Agreement.

Figure 7: This section appears at the top of the website's homepage, providing the most concise information about RE4GREEN.

Figure 8: This will be featured below the section depicted in Figure 7 and will contain detailed (but still high-level) information about RE4GREEN.

Learn more about the **Project**

Introduction: Human Embeddedness in Nature
Prof. Dirk Lanzerath

Watch Video

Welcome Speech
Prof. Andreas Zimmer

Watch Video

Mapping the project's concepts, pt. 1
Re4Green consortium

Watch Video

Figure 9: This will be featured on the homepage and will contain links to several videos from the kick-off meeting, introducing viewers to key project themes and concepts.

Social Labs

The RE4GREEN Social Labs are participatory spaces where individuals from diverse backgrounds and experiences across various fields collaborate to discuss climate and environmental ethics and research integrity issues related to EU research and innovation in general and also research and innovation deployed specifically to support the Green Transition

HEALTH. INCLUSIVE SOCIETY. CIVIL SECURITY FOR SOCIETY

👁

DIGITAL INDUSTRY AND SPACE

👁

CLIMATE AND MOBILITY

👁

ENERGY

👁

FOOD, BIOECONOMY, AGRICULTURE / ENVIRONMENT

👁

SOIL, WATERS, OCEANS, NATURAL RESOURCES

👁

Figure 10: This part of the homepage will contain basic information about the Social Lab methodology employed within RE4GREEN. Each box will link to the subpages of the different Social Labs, each containing a more detailed description of the respective Lab.

Basic Objectives

Map & Identify	+
Build a Community	+
Produce & Complement	-
operational ethics & integrity guidelines, including the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, & elaborate recommendations to account for environmental & climate ethics	
Develop & Implement	+

Figure 11: This part of the homepage will outline the objectives of RE4GREEN.

Subscribe to our Newsletter

Subscribe

See Our Activity

Visit

Visit

Figure 12: Here, the visitor can subscribe to the project's newsletter and view RE4GREEN's activity on the websites of networks like the Embassy of Good Science and ENERI.

Main Output

Guidelines

Operational climate and environmental ethics and integrity guidelines

Policy Recommendations

Integrating climate and environmental ethics into ethics and integrity resources

Training Materials

Programmes to ensure R&I activities holistically contribute to the Green Transition

Target Groups

- **Researchers & Research Performing Organisations**
- **Industry**
- **Research ethics committee members**
- **Research integrity experts**
- **Research managers and administrators**
- **Policymakers**
- **General Public**

Figure 13: This part of the homepage describes RE4GREEN's main outputs and the target groups of the project.

Figure 14: The logos of the consortium members, along with an acknowledgement to our funders, have been placed at the bottom of the homepage.

Social media

RE4GREEN will disseminate and communicate project progress and results via the social media platforms X and LinkedIn. As a platform focused on exchange and interaction with users, X will be utilised for both dissemination and communication purposes. LinkedIn, on the other hand, which is focused on content distribution within professional communities, will be utilised mainly for dissemination purposes. Although both platforms provide little flexibility for substantive branding, WP5 leaders have used all available means to customise the RE4GREEN profiles. Figure 15 and 16 present the application of RE4GREEN branding to X and LinkedIn, respectively.

The use and choice of specific social media platforms will be monitored continuously throughout the project. In addition, RE4GREEN's social media channels will stay active for at least three years after the end of the project.

Figure 15: RE4GREEN branding, as applied to X.

Figure 16: RE4GREEN branding, as applied to LinkedIn.

PowerPoint template

Figure 17 presents the PowerPoint template of RE4GREEN. This template is important since all presentations on RE4GREEN (e.g., conferences, workshops, cluster meeting dissemination events, and public engagement events) will use these slide designs.

Figure 17: RE4GREEN branding, as applied to a PowerPoint presentation.

Deliverable template

This report presents the deliverable template for RE4GREEN. Special emphasis has been placed not only on providing a placeholder for all needed information but also on enhancing the aesthetic and visual appeal of project outputs. This attention to design is important, given that nearly all RE4GREEN deliverables are publicly available. Consequently, they are intended not only as technical reports but also as additional tools for dissemination and communication.

Conclusion

This report has emphasised the importance of RE4GREEN's branding in achieving its goal of supporting a holistic ethics and integrity framework for R&I. Using a bold, unique, and consistent logo, colour scheme, typography, and design across its website, social media channels, and templates, RE4GREEN will effectively reach a wide audience and engage a diverse set of stakeholders.

In the coming months, WP5 will augment the RE4GREEN DEC content using the branding approach outlined herein. Among other activities, it will expand the RE4GREEN website to reflect project progress and published reports. In addition, a RE4GREEN space will be created within the ENERI Classroom and the Embassy of Good Science, hubs for EU-funded Coordination and Support Actions (CSA) projects that deal with research ethics- and integrity-related challenges. WP5 will also adapt and monitor key performance indicators (KPIs) within RE4GREEN's "Plan for communication, dissemination, and exploitation" (D5.2) to assess the effectiveness of the project's visual identity.

